

Economics and Business Management

16(3), 09-26

Journal homepage: <https://economicscience.com.ua/en>

Received: 01.05.2025 Revised: 13.08.2025 Accepted: 23.09.2025

UDC 338.242

DOI: 10.31548/economics/3.2025.09

Diana Shelenko*

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University
76010, 57 Shevchenko Str., Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9214-7258>

Oleksandr Shpykuliak

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
National Scientific Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics"
03127, 10 Heroiv Oborony Str., Kyiv, Ukraine
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5257-5517>

Ivan Balaniuk

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University
76010, 57 Shevchenko Str., Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8320-6383>

Hennadii Mazur

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
PHEE "Vinnytsia Academy of Continuing Education"
21050, 13 Hrushevskoho Str., Vinnytsia, Ukraine
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5061-1817>

Yaroslav Boichuk

Postgraduate Student
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University
76010, 57 Shevchenko Str., Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-0793-905X>

Monitoring and assessment of the competitiveness of products, goods, and services in the context of innovative entrepreneurship development

Abstract. Innovative entrepreneurship is key to economic stability and competitiveness, requiring improved decision-making tools through enhanced monitoring and evaluation of product competitiveness. The purpose of this study was to theoretically and methodologically substantiate and characterise institutional capabilities for monitoring the competitiveness of products, goods, and services in the development of innovative entrepreneurship structures. The research proposed

Suggested Citation:

Shelenko, D., Shpykuliak, O., Balaniuk, I., Mazur, H., & Boichuk, Ya. (2025). Monitoring and assessment of the competitiveness of products, goods, and services in the context of innovative entrepreneurship development. *Economics and Business Management*, 16(3), 9-26. doi: 10.31548/economics/3.2025.09.

*Corresponding author

Copyright © The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

conceptual foundations for a system of competitiveness monitoring, analytical tools for evaluating and forecasting enterprise positions, and an assessment framework that considered both internal and external influencing factors. Special emphasis was placed on understanding how these factors affected market positioning and the functional development of innovative structures. The study improved methodological foundations for competitiveness monitoring, particularly in light of institutional transformations in the market exchange environment. A key contribution was the introduction of a comprehensive approach that incorporated production costs, human resources, innovation potential, financial stability, market supply, and managerial efficiency. This approach went beyond static measurements to capture structural dynamics over time, revealing interrelations between various competitiveness factors across different periods and contexts. Combining quantitative and qualitative assessment tools enabled a more holistic analysis of how internal and external influences impacted the performance of innovation-oriented enterprises and overall entrepreneurial effectiveness. Key assessment dimensions included production efficiency, human capital, innovation input, financial soundness, product and service quality, and their synergetic effects. These insights were essential for enhancing strategic and managerial decision-making in a rapidly evolving market environment. The practical significance of the study was positioned in proposing an improved mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the competitiveness of products, goods, and services in the context of the development of innovative entrepreneurship

Keywords: economic growth; evaluation of goods and services; sustainable development; entrepreneur

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the entrepreneurship development, the competitiveness of products, goods and services in enterprises has a causal relationship and is subject to the diverse risks of the destructive impact of the military factor. In addition to the classical institutionalisation to market conditions, the development of competitiveness in wartime is subject to atypical, unpredictable risks that determine the decline in economic capacity, innovation, and vice versa – de-innovation and possible physical loss of business. In practice, in particular, the structure of innovative entrepreneurship, and a priori, all other entrepreneurial formations, institutionally and economically face numerous challenges of a high-risk market environment. A managerial response to such multiple challenges is possible as a result of the use of effective methods of monitoring the evaluation of goods and services and their positioning in the market for the implementation of decisions in the business practice of transactions.

L. Sas *et al.* (2022) asserted that the creation of a competitive business was impossible without the systematic implementation of technological innovations, as they served as a catalyst for increasing the efficiency of production

processes and contributed to the long-term sustainability of the enterprise. H.A. Al-Ababneh *et al.* (2021) emphasised that organisational and managerial changes should encompass not only individual business processes but also be integrated into the overall management system. Under a holistic approach to managerial innovations, it was possible to ensure the growth of enterprise competitiveness. N. Pylypiv & S. Sologub (2024) highlighted the importance of developing a comprehensive and adaptive enterprise development strategy that integrated all components of innovative activity. The strategy they proposed was intended to cover the entire life cycle of innovations, ensuring their systematic implementation and orientation toward long-term sustainable growth.

The development of a systematic approach to the evaluation of goods and services was expected to consider several key aspects identified by D. Shelenko *et al.* (2024), including the methodology of integrated assessment, optimisation of logistics processes, adaptability of logistics structures, advancement of local logistics hubs, and enhancement of risk resilience. According to the researchers, selecting an optimal logistics route enabled the most effective delivery of raw

materials, goods, packaging, transportation, and storage. Logistic solutions not only determined the transactional dynamics of goods and services movement but also significantly affected the spatial organisation of economic activity of enterprises and the quality of life of the population. O. Priss *et al.* (2023) emphasised that the development of a comfortable urban environment directly depended on the level of accessibility of basic goods, in particular food products. Restricted access to environmentally safe goods in cities can lead to socio-economic imbalance and a decline in quality of life. Ensuring broad access to environmentally friendly products is a key factor for the sustainable development of urban areas, where cultural ecosystem services (CES) play a motivational role in harmoniously combining economic and social aspects through thoughtful planning of commercial communities and ecological infrastructure (Kozak *et al.*, 2024).

The problem on the way to a correct assessment of the competitiveness of products, goods and services was financial support, and the main factors in the development of competition policy as proven by I.V. Babii *et al.* (2022), were intellectual resources, a flexible management system, motivation, and a key sustainable element that, despite uncertainty, maintained stability and served as the basis for development. The researchers emphasised the following key aspects of the success of entrepreneurial structures: provision of finance and building an effective competition policy. Monitoring and evaluation of product competitiveness are key tools for adapting the agricultural sector to challenges in wartime conditions. The development trends of agricultural enterprises projected T. Kuzmin *et al.* (2024) by 2030 indicated the necessity of implementing a systematic approach to resource utilisation, labour productivity development, and the implementation of enterprises' innovation potential. I.F. Balaniuk & T.L. Ivaniuk (2020) emphasised that improving soil fertility and optimising land use required advanced monitoring methods to assess both production and resource management outcomes.

In the context of ensuring the competitiveness of products, goods, and services of innovative entrepreneurship, attention is focused

on state price regulation as a factor that, on the one hand, restrains the development of business entities, and on the other, ensures market stability. Competitiveness is formed based on a complex interconnection between the qualitative characteristics of products, their compliance with international standards, innovativeness, pricing, logistical and marketing decisions, and adherence to regulatory requirements. The research problem considered a set of economic factors: production costs, human and innovation potential, financial stability, management efficiency, and adaptability to market changes. In this context, the purpose of the study was realised through the theoretical and methodological definition of how institutional capabilities were used to monitor the competitiveness of products, goods, and services during the development of innovative entrepreneurship structures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study of the system for monitoring the development and economic assessment of the competitiveness of products, goods, and services in the development of business structures in 2018-2022 was based on an integrated approach that combined conceptual, methodological, and analytical approaches to assessing the competitive position of enterprises in a dynamic market environment. The period of 2018-2022 was chosen by the authors due to the availability and completeness of statistical data that had undergone official verification, whereas the data for 2023-2024 have not yet been published, which limited the possibility of using them in the study. The limitation of the research period ensured the reliability and representativeness of the analytical conclusions. The informational basis of the study was formed based on statistical data (State Statistics Service of Ukraine, n.d.), official strategic planning documents (Development Strategy..., 2020), analytical reports of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (used for the analysis of enterprises' innovation activity (OECD & Eurostat, 2018)), informational resources (the PDCA cycle approach was applied as a tool of managerial control and continuous improvement (PDCA cycle explained, 2025)), publications of international organisations, and the results of the analysis of

studies in the field of monitoring and evaluation of the competitiveness of products, goods, and services in the context of the development of innovative entrepreneurship. The combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis methods provided a comprehensive vision of the dynamics of competitiveness of products, goods, and services under the conditions of institutional changes in the market environment.

The study used theoretical substantiation (a study of the main scientific approaches to assessing the competitiveness of products, goods and services); identification of the main factors and influencing factors (a scheme of influence of factors and factors of competitiveness of products, goods and services). System analysis was applied by the researchers to understand the relationships between competitiveness factors and to assess their impact on business entities. The structural and functional approach was used to identify the key components of the monitoring system for assessing each of the factors of enterprise competitiveness. The choice of these methods was driven by the need to combine quantitative and qualitative analysis, which allowed for a deeper understanding of the priority criteria for assessing goods and services and the areas of development of business structures, their adaptation to crisis conditions, and the introduction of innovative management approaches. Economic and statistical analysis helped to identify key trends in the structure of small businesses, while a systematic approach allowed for the integration of this data into the broader context of sustainable development. The use of integrated methods of analysis and evaluation was aimed at increasing the competitive position of entrepreneurship through the optimal combination of internal resources and external market factors.

The study of the subject matter was focused on the general economic assessment of the trends in the development of product competitiveness with a projection onto the roles of the innovatisation of entrepreneurship, and on outlining the capacity of institutional innovations to ensure effectiveness. The applied methodology of institutional analysis was developed within the framework of consolidating the identification of the results of interaction between

economic, social, political, and regulatory factors that influenced the competitiveness of goods on the market in alignment with the statuses of innovative entrepreneurship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessment of the competitiveness of products, goods, and services is a key condition for achieving success in the market. This state of affairs in industry can be achieved only through the active implementation of innovative technologies and by entering the market with products that meet the requirements of knowledge intensity and competitiveness. These characteristics should be integrated into all industries, especially those that determine technological progress (production of technological equipment, computer equipment, communications equipment, and other products that form the basis for innovative economic development) (Development Strategy..., 2020). O. Stakhiv & T. Adamchuk (2017) suggest that product competitiveness determines the competitiveness of an organisation in any short period of time – it is a necessary but not sufficient condition for its achievement. V. Nychyporenko (2018) proved that the ability of commodity producers to produce certain advantages for themselves in a competitive market environment to achieve competitiveness is formed by the use of scientific and technological progress in the system of labour organisation, production, and management. That is, competition is a powerful incentive, and the means of forming business competitiveness is the introduction of innovative solutions to improve labour organisation and management, which contributes to improving product quality, reducing costs and ensuring their competitiveness in the market.

The modernisation of enterprises covers several levels of management (institutional: the enterprise, a specific type of product/service; functional: by areas of modernisation of individual economic sectors and the organisation of market transactions, at the level of the structural units of the enterprise), ensuring the effective use of resources and the transformation of innovations into concrete competitive advantages (Tulchynska *et al.*, 2021). The outlined vision helped to define areas for ensuring the effective use of resources and the

transformation of innovations into specific competitive advantages. The strategy for the development of agriculture and rural areas in Ukraine identified areas for assessing the competitiveness of goods, considering several key aspects: restoration and improvement of agriculture focused on the production of high value-added goods; increasing the competitiveness of Ukrainian agricultural products; increasing the role of food systems; fair distribution of income for all producers, regardless of their scale; inclusive access to finance (Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1163-p, 2024). The selected steps are necessary for the development of sustainable competitive advantages in the agricultural sector. The key areas for analysing the competitiveness of products and goods can be: product quality, pricing, cost, innovation potential, marketing and branding; logistics and accessibility, market share, social and environmental responsibility, competitors, demand and consumers. That is, competitiveness can be assessed by comparing competitors' products with each other (Slyvinska & Bodnar, 2019).

Assessment of product quality means compliance with standards, consumer characteristics, and innovation. Methods of quality control of goods and services should outline spot checks that will be carried out in the absence of economic or technical grounds for the main inspection. The European HACCP system has been implemented at 49 food and processing companies in the Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast, including 6 companies that are authorised to export products to the EU and the Customs Union. Due to investment attraction, the region has implemented projects to create new and reconstruct existing production facilities of agro-industrial enterprises (Development Strategy..., 2020).

The SWOT analysis of the Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast Development Strategy for 2021-2027 (Development Strategy..., 2020) and the scenario-based approaches to spatial planning through 2027 indicate an aspiration for the balanced use of the region's natural resource potential, the strengthening of infrastructure development, and the reduction of intra-regional disparities. The results of the SWOT analysis, developed by the regional working group and the coordination council of Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast, allowed

the authors to reconsider and generalise the conclusions of the official strategic document that influenced the potential of the region. In the context of Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast, the SWOT analysis considered the dynamics of socio-economic development, the state of infrastructure, human resources potential, available natural resources, and investment attractiveness. The identified threats, in particular trade restrictions imposed by key international partners, were assessed as one of the potentially restraining external factors that may affect the effectiveness and innovativeness of the implementation of regional economic policy in the context of European integration. The main areas of development of Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast include the modernisation of traditional industries (mining and chemical, oil and gas, wood processing), ecological rehabilitation of industry, development of interregional cooperation due to the cross-border location, and social integration of rural and mountain areas. The comprehensive analysis of existing economic and social preconditions, carried out based on the study (Development Strategy..., 2020), did not allow the authors to define a single strategic development path. This caused the need for multi-directional planning, considering three possible scenarios – inertial, innovative, and intermediate. These scenarios reflect the need for flexible institutional responses to internal challenges and external changes to ensure the stability of regional innovative entrepreneurship.

In 2021, according to the Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1163-p (2024), the majority of food products sold by retailers were produced in Ukraine, including more than 92% of meat and meat products, bakery and flour confectionery, more than 85% of edible oils and fats, soft drinks, more than 73% of sugar confectionery, tobacco products, more than 67% of processed fruits and vegetables, and alcoholic beverages. Exploring the areas of quality assessment of goods and services based on the example of the PDCA cycle (plan-do-check-act) in the food industry (PDCA cycle explained, 2025): set product safety goals (reduce the risk of infection); implement changes (modify sanitary procedures); monitor product safety indicators and verify their compliance; standardise effective sanitary

practices and include them in product safety protocols. This approach ensures continuous improvement of processes and vouches for the compliance of products with established quality and safety standards. However, the competitiveness of products, goods, and services is formed under the influence of various factors and factors, the interaction of which is shown in Figure 1.

The scheme described in Figure 1 will provide a basis for analysing the factors that influence competitiveness and those that contribute to the development of effective strategies for

improving the competitive position of enterprises. To create and coordinate effective strategies for increasing the competitive position of enterprises, innovation and technological level will play a decisive role, due to the introduction of advanced technologies, automation and diversification in production processes, digitalisation of business processes, Blockchain, the use of online marketing, e-commerce platforms, feedback systems for forming a strong connection with end users and active use of scientific research, innovative entrepreneurship entities.

Figure 1. Scheme of influence of factors and factors of competitiveness of products, goods and services

Source: developed by the authors based on M. Ivanova *et al.* (2018), K. Decyk (2020), H.A. Al-Ababneh *et al.* (2021), I.V. Babii *et al.* (2022), I.O. Korchynskiy & M.I. Shchadylo (2022), V. Kovalchuk (2023)

Analysing Figure 1, a correlation is observed between product quality, compliance with international standards, innovativeness, pricing, marketing, logistics, and regulatory requirements due to their synergistic impact on enterprise competitiveness. High quality and certification according to international standards (ISO, HACCP) enhance consumer trust and facilitate entry into foreign markets, while

innovativeness ensures technological advantage and production efficiency. Optimal pricing, a well-developed marketing strategy, and logistics allow for cost reduction and stable demand. The regulatory environment and wartime conditions define the general framework for enterprises' operations, particularly for innovative entrepreneurship, highlighting factors of state support and institutional conditions for market

accessibility. The overall effect of these factors determines enterprises' market position, financial stability, and ability to achieve balanced development. It follows that enterprises take a comprehensive approach to assessing and strengthening their competitiveness, gaining the ability not only to maintain their market positions but also to expand their presence, thereby increasing their resilience in conditions of economic uncertainty and turbulence.

Innovative activity contributes to the creation of competitive advantages, ensuring that business structures are sustainable in the face of market changes and resume their activities after the end of the war. With this in mind, the paper identifies opportunities for assessing goods and services in terms of their compliance with market conditions and adaptation to crisis situations. Innovations play a key role in improving living standards, affecting different economic levels – from individuals to entire sectors and countries, which allows the contribution to socio-economic development to be assessed and increases the effectiveness of public policy by adapting to dynamic changes (OECD & Eurostat, 2018). An innovation, as defined in the "Oslo Manual" methodological document, is a new or improved product or process that differs significantly from previous products or processes of the unit and that has been made available to potential users (product) or put into use by the unit (process), product innovation is a new or improved product or service that differs significantly from the enterprise's previous products or services and has been introduced to the market (OECD & Eurostat, 2018).

Innovations allow creating unique products, goods, and services with high added value, which, in turn, ensures competitive advantages in the EU market. The experience of leading companies such as Apple, Google (Alphabet), and Pfizer has demonstrated that enterprises that systematically invest significant funds in research and development (R&D) exhibit greater adaptability to changes in the market environment. For example, in 2023, Apple allocated approximately 29.9 billion USD to R&D (YB Case, 2024). Alphabet invested 45.4 billion USD in this area in 2023. The experience of Alphabet (the parent company of Google) in 2023

demonstrated a strategic focus on the development of artificial intelligence as a key factor of competitiveness. In the fourth quarter of 2023, total advertising revenue increased by 11% year-over-year, although it did not meet analysts' expectations. The company introduced a new generative AI model – Gemini, which is integrated into all Google products, including the Bard search system and advertising tools. Gemini reduced search latency by 40% and improved the quality of the customer experience. Artificial intelligence plays a key role in marketing campaigns, potentially reaching more than 3 billion users with an increase in conversion rates for retailers. In the context of monitoring and evaluating the competitiveness of products in the digital services market, the example of Google Corporation (Alphabet Inc.) is illustrative of the effective implementation of innovations in strategic business models. In the fourth quarter of 2023, profit from the Google Cloud segment reached 9.1 billion USD, which exceeded the figure of the corresponding period of the previous year by 26% (George, 2024). The synergistic interaction between information technologies, creative content, and innovative infrastructure contributed to the creation of high value-added products, which had a positive impact on their competitiveness assessment.

Awareness of these processes is important for assessing the factors of enterprise competitiveness. To evaluate each of the factors of competitiveness of business structures, Figure 2 was constructed by the authors. Monitoring of the assessment of each of the factors of enterprise competitiveness allows adapting the assessment to the specifics of particular sectors of the economy, which enhances the possibilities of practical application of this methodology. The innovativeness of this approach can be seen in the combination of conventional assessment methods with advanced analytical tools, including econometric modelling and the Stella computer programme, which will allow innovative businesses not only to identify their weaknesses but also to develop a forecast, work out possible scenarios for the development of the competitive environment and ways to adapt the developed strategy to strengthen their market positions.

Figure 2. Monitoring of the evaluation of competitiveness factors of business structures

Source: authors' research

Marketing and branding are important factors in the competitiveness of products, goods and services, and even high-quality products require proper promotion. Marketing with a projection to the future will involve the development of strong market positions, the acquisition of new skills, and combining them with previously acquired ones, acclimatisation to changes in demand and the creation of unique value propositions for consumers by innovative enterprises. The introduction of branding of innovative enterprises increases customer loyalty and reduces sensitivity to price competition, and the use of digital marketing elements, social networks and personalised offers increases

the reach of a new target audience, thereby expanding markets. Focusing on the evaluation of marketing tools will not only assess the competitiveness of goods and services, but also promote the development of entrepreneurial activity through the development of long-term relationships with the market, emphasising the importance of human resources.

The implementation of branding is an innovative practice for enhancing the competitiveness of products and business entities. This practice is implemented through measures aimed at ensuring the uniqueness of product design, forming an emotional connection between the product and the consumer, and creating a

stable motivation for purchase through a high level of trust in the product. The functionality of branding, being a priority in ensuring enterprise competitiveness, is implemented through achieving increased sales, customer loyalty, brand recognition, and adaptive pricing policy. A practical example was the introduction of the national brand Ukraine NOW, which influenced Ukraine's competitiveness by contributing to its positive perception on the international stage, attracting investment, and developing tourism potential, in particular: improving its international image (Ukraine ranked 44th, indicating the growth of its soft power and recognition on the global stage according to the Global Soft Power Index 2024 by Brand Finance) (Ukraine – country..., 2024); the official Ukraine.ua page on Instagram reached 1 million followers, entering the TOP-5 national profiles in the world (Brand Ukraine, 2022). These practices influence competitiveness by creating the potential for Ukrainian-produced goods and services to enter and establish themselves in international markets.

In the Ukrainian market, the platforms Rozetka and Monobank actively use behavioural analytics and dynamic offers, which allow them to remain among the TOP-5 most well-known brands in Ukraine according to MMR (2023). Rozetka actively uses behavioural analytics and dynamic offers to personalise the user experience, which enabled it to become the leader in online commerce in Ukraine with revenue of 45 billion UAH in 2023, exceeding pre-war figures (The Ukrainian retail..., 2024). Monobank implements personalised financial products and communications, which contributed to the growth of its client base to 10 million users as of 2025. The bank received numerous awards for innovation and customer orientation (Monobank – chronicles..., 2023).

In the global market, branding is implemented by Netflix, Amazon, and YouTube, which use algorithmic models to generate personalised recommendations that contribute to increasing viewing time and enhancing user satisfaction, and are based on users' behavioural patterns. According to statistics, 75% of the content viewed on Netflix comes through personalised recommendations (Personalized recommendations..., 2023). The company Chewy,

which supplies pet products, has implemented deep customer orientation: if a customer stops making purchases due to the loss of a pet, the brand sends personalised letters with words of sympathy, which increases emotional engagement, long-term customer loyalty, and strengthens the emotional connection with the brand (What does..., 2023).

The effectiveness of any strategy depends on the professionalism and motivation of the staff, including young people. Young and creative professionals can generate new ideas, implement innovations and dynamically adapt to changes in the business environment. Investing in employee training, participation of employees in international congresses and industry forums, and organising a corporate culture that supports initiative are positive factors that contribute to increased productivity and reduced staff turnover. In view of this, human capital development is a long-term strategy that ensures a steady increase in the competitiveness of innovative enterprises. Thus, investments in the development of labour potential contribute not only to increasing labour productivity but also to optimising business processes. In turn, the ability to control and manage costs is of key importance and opens up opportunities for effective influence on the level of competitiveness of enterprises. Considering the mentioned trends, it is advisable to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the impact of monitoring mechanisms and economic evaluation of competitiveness on the resilience and adaptability of entrepreneurial structures. The generalised organisational and economic aspects of this process are presented in Table 1.

The analysis of organisational and economic trends in innovation activity in Ukraine indicates certain structural changes in entrepreneurial dynamics in 2020-2022 compared to 2018-2020. The total number of enterprises across all economic sectors decreased by 2,216 units due to factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic, changes in the business environment, and increasing entrepreneurial risks. Simultaneously, the number of innovative enterprises increased by 306 units, indicating the growing role of innovation strategies in ensuring business competitiveness.

Table 1. Organisational and economic trends of innovation activity in the development of entrepreneurship in Ukraine, 2018-2022

Indicators	Total economy		Including:			
			Industry		Manufacture of food products, beverages, and tobacco products	
	Period – Years					
	2018-2020	2020-2022	2018-2020	2020-2022	2018-2020	2020-2022
Number of enterprises (innovative and non-innovative), units	26,904	24,688	12,072	11,459	2,096	1,876
Number of innovative enterprises, units	2,283	2,589	1,552	1,611	317	305
<i>Structural changes by indicators:</i>						
	Number of enterprises (innovative and non-innovative)				Number of innovative enterprises	
2020-2022 vs. 2018-2020 – total economy	-2,216 – (decrease)				+306 – (increase)	
2020-2022 vs. 2018-2020 – industry	- 613 – (decrease)				+52 – (increase)	
2020-2022 vs. 2018-2020 – manufacture of food products, beverages, and tobacco products	-220 – (decrease)				- 12 – (decrease)	

Source: State Statistics Service of Ukraine (n.d.) and authors' calculations

A similar trend is observed in the industrial sector, reflecting the transformation of the manufacturing sector towards technological modernisation and the implementation of innovative approaches to improve efficiency. The most negative dynamics were recorded in the manufacture of food products, beverages, and tobacco products. The total number of enterprises decreased by 220 units, while the number of innovative enterprises declined by 12 units, suggesting a decrease in innovation activity in this segment. Changes in the enterprise structure highlight the need to improve the monitoring system for product, goods, and service competitiveness. Thus, monitoring mechanisms and economic evaluation of competitiveness directly influence the adaptability and resilience of entrepreneurial structures.

Conceptual assessments of the implementation of capabilities and the achievement of competitiveness effects of products by business entities based on innovativeness have shown the following. Firstly, enterprises that are actively involved in the innovation diffusion ecosystem generally demonstrate stronger competitive

advantages in their manufactured products. Secondly, effective competitive strategies for enhancing the competitiveness of products of innovative enterprises are based on the application of a wide range of innovative practices (organisational and economic integration into new markets, diversification of production and distribution channels). Thirdly, examples of innovativeness can be observed in various business models and sectors (for example, the development of enterprises through integration and promotion of products to European markets, and the innovative transformation of food production along the “from farm to fork” chain), with a focus on optimising value creation, improving value redistribution, and reducing transaction costs. Fourthly, there are clear practical results of the institutional diffusion of innovations.

This is especially evident in areas where institutional consolidation of innovations takes place and interaction between participants of the innovation ecosystem is supported. Among the manifestations of innovation activity and the results of institutionalisation of innovative development, the following can be noted:

- construction of high-tech livestock farms;
- creation of grain storage and transportation systems, especially under conditions of radical transformation of product distribution channels due to reorientation to the European market;
- development of cluster and cooperative organisations that have improved market integration of small producers, in particular the onion cluster, which represents institutional consolidation of small onion producers (Agroportal, n.d.a);
- creation of water user organisations, which contribute to increased yields of agricultural crops (Agroportal, n.d.b);
- a specialised cooperative for bean processing – the “Stryiskyi Yas” cooperative, which has entered the processing stage (Agroportal, 2025a);
- development of the organic sector and the biofuel production sector, including newly built biomethane plants (Agroportal, 2025b), and the industrial park “Bio-Lan”, specialising in bioethanol and biogas processing (Ukrainian truth, 2025).

The conducted analysis allows stating that innovations in the field of entrepreneurship, particularly in the most resilient sectors of Ukraine’s economy under wartime conditions, play a key role in strengthening market survival potential. Innovation strategies implemented at all levels of the value chain, and within the interaction infrastructure between business entities, have a strong impact on ensuring business success and profitability. When assessing the effectiveness of innovation activity, including the performance of innovative entrepreneurship in Ukraine, it should be noted that according to various estimates – in 2023: Ukraine ranked 55th in the Global Innovation Index (Kovalchuk, 2023); state support for innovation activity is imperfect (Yehorov *et al.*, 2023); the process of transforming innovation policy, in particular its adaptation to EU requirements, is ongoing.

The most effective mechanisms for implementing innovations in entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine were identified through the application of an institutional approach, which helped to analyse the effectiveness of existing practices and to outline the potential for their evolution under the conditions of structural changes in the economy. In particular, based on the example of the agricultural sector of the economy, it was determined that the most effective were innovative

practices and competitive strategies based on the principles of diversification and cooperation for the implementation of institutional innovations. The evaluation results identified the most effective approaches to strengthening enterprises’ competitive advantages and ensuring their long-term market sustainability. Primarily, this concerns adaptive cost management strategies that optimise production processes and increase profitability. Investing in the development of human and innovation potential played a crucial role, as did the existing institutional capacity for implementing cutting-edge technologies. Financial stability is ensured through effective risk management and flexible pricing policies. At the same time, product and service quality, consumer-oriented approaches, and adherence to environmental standards have become key factors in maintaining competitive advantages in a dynamic market environment.

The assessment of goods and services involves analysing brand awareness, the effectiveness of advertising campaigns, the level of consumer loyalty, and the compliance of agricultural products with modern market trends, such as organic production, green business, and environmental friendliness. Particular attention should be paid to the development of unique regional brands and craftsmanship. Craft agricultural products can be represented by honey, hutsul cheese, chocolate, drinks, jams, sausages, etc. Recognition of craft products or goods will popularise Ukraine in international markets and contribute to the development of rural areas. The growing interest in unique and authentic products is also generating demand for craft products, which allows them to integrate into global retail chains. In this context, consumer loyalty is determined by the level of trust in products based on quality, environmental responsibility of producers, and social orientation of agricultural enterprises.

Market share research will help to analyse the position of a product, analyse the position of a product on the market and the dynamics of its changes. Securing a product’s place in the market will allow manufacturers to maintain their position in the global market through innovation, sustainability, and uniqueness of their offer. In general, effective strategic positioning

is based on a comprehensive approach to competitive analysis, which allows for assessing current market trends and adapting business models in line with industry dynamics. Competitor assessment will include an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the main competitors. By working together, producers of goods and services can create a platform for creating high-quality competitive products backed by geographical indications, which will provide not only economic benefits but also cultural and social uniqueness of products.

The results are consistent with the study by M. Ivanova *et al.* (2018), which proposes an integral approach to assessing competitiveness, including the analysis of three main types of economic activity: supply, production, and sales. Evaluating each of these aspects using independent indicators allows for a comprehensive identification of a company's strengths and weaknesses. This study highlights the need to expand this approach, particularly by considering factors of innovation activity and digital transformation, which significantly impact the competitive resilience of modern enterprises. The obtained results are consistent with the findings of O.M. Mukan & A.M. Sharuk (2021), who emphasise the importance of an industry-specific approach to assessing the competitiveness of enterprises. However, the conducted study indicates the need to supplement their approach with empirical data that quantitatively determine the effectiveness of different assessment methods in specific economic sectors.

Similarly, the conclusions of I. Korchynskyi & M. Shchadylo (2022) regarding the dynamics of competition and the impact of economic changes on business structures are confirmed by the results of the present study. However, in the context of digital transformation and the growing importance of environmental sustainability, their study requires an expanded analysis that considers new challenges in enterprises' adaptation to rapid changes in the business environment. The comparison of the findings of the present study with the paper by K. Decyk (2020), which emphasises the relationship between innovation activity and enterprise competitiveness, confirms the importance of strategic innovation management. The research highlights

that the impact of innovations on competitive advantages largely depends on the level of investment profitability and the ability of enterprises to effectively integrate new technologies into their business processes, which requires a deeper empirical analysis.

The results of the present study correlate with the findings of R.P. Pradhan *et al.* (2020), which demonstrate the interconnection between entrepreneurship, innovation, and economic growth. The analysis confirms that enterprises contribute to economic development through investments in technology, job creation, and the expansion of market competition. However, unlike the generalised conclusions of R.P. Pradhan *et al.*, the present study reveals that the impact of innovation activity on enterprise competitiveness varies significantly depending on industry specifics and regional conditions, requiring further refinement of innovation entrepreneurship development strategies. The results are consistent with the findings of a number of recent scientific studies on the state of innovative entrepreneurship in Ukraine. V. Kovalchuk (2023), in his paper, stated that despite the existence of certain innovation potential, the institutional environment in Ukraine remains ineffective for its full realisation. This was confirmed by Ukraine's position in the Global Innovation Index, where in 2023 it ranked 55th among 132 countries. The results obtained by the researchers partially support these conclusions, especially regarding the insufficient systemic support for innovation from institutions.

Contextually significant for the study of the competitiveness of products, goods, and services of innovative entrepreneurship was the approach of B. Milward (2025), who emphasised the importance of creativity in management, organisation, and production technologies as key factors of competitiveness. The researcher highlighted the role of asymmetric strategies and tactics at all levels of economic system positioning, which aligned with the operational practices of innovation-active enterprises. H. Kapinos & K. Larionova (2025) emphasised the importance of strategic management of the innovative development of an enterprise as a way to implement innovation policy, which agrees with the belief in the importance of the systematic

diffusion of innovations. In the development of innovative entrepreneurship, the processes of continuous implementation of innovations and their diffusion as both a product and a tool for their creation play a key role. These processes form the basis for achieving not only competitiveness but also the resilience of enterprises in a dynamic market environment.

In academic literature, special attention was paid to the adaptability of specific sectors of the national economy to both external and internal challenges. Based on the analysis proposed by A. Yakymchuk *et al.* (2021), an assessment was conducted of the methods for calculating integral indicators of Ukraine's economic security. The study revealed mostly medium and low values of the integral indicator and pointed to the need for stronger institutional support. This finding is consistent with the conclusions of the current study, particularly concerning the limited effectiveness of national policies in stimulating innovation-driven development. According to the study by V. Hotra (2024), state regulation of the limits of retail price growth and the timing of their official publication shapes institutional conditions that simultaneously influence both market stability and the adaptability of innovative enterprises.

The obtained results complement the existing research and show that the influence of state price regulation, on the one hand, ensures transparency in pricing policy, while on the other hand, it may limit the flexibility of business entities under changing market conditions. In this context, a critical discussion of existing methodologies is essential to develop a more dynamic and adaptable approach to competitiveness assessment – one that not only reflects past trends but also anticipates future shifts in the economic landscape. The proposed areas for assessing the competitiveness of products, goods and services provide a systematic approach to assessing competitiveness and forming an effective strategy for the development of economic structures.

CONCLUSIONS

In a turbulent market environment, the effectiveness of methods for assessing the competitiveness of products, goods and services in the

development of innovative entrepreneurship structures depends on the flexibility of their adaptation to a rapidly changing economic environment. The active combination of conventional assessment methods with advanced digital analytical tools allows innovative enterprises to obtain more accurate and reasonable results and is a key factor in making effective management decisions. The findings became the basis for identifying priority criteria for evaluating goods and services that will help to support the competitiveness of business structures in Ukraine in the face of current challenges, in particular, the study showed that digitalisation and the introduction of innovative tools are important in the evaluation of goods and services, as they help to increase their competitiveness in various ecosystems.

Assessment of the competitiveness of goods and services is based on a comprehensive analysis of both internal factors (quality, innovation, costs) and external factors (consumer demand, market dynamics, social and environmental trends). Strategic marketing allows companies to adapt their products to changing market conditions and increase their value in the eyes of consumers. Monitoring the assessment of each of the factors of competitiveness of business structures is an important strategic management tool that allows identification the strengths and weaknesses of the business model in a timely manner, adjust production processes to changes in the market, and increase efficiency in making management decisions. The analysis of the dynamics of indicators showed a general decrease in the number of enterprises in the Ukrainian economy during 2020-2022 compared to 2018-2020, particularly in the food industry, where the number of both total and innovative enterprises declined (by 220 and 12 units, respectively). A positive aspect was that, despite the overall reduction in the number of enterprises, the industrial sector as a whole recorded an increase in the number of innovation-active units (+52), indicating a concentration of innovation efforts in more resilient industries.

The obtained results have certain limitations: the analysis was conducted based on available statistical data, which does not always fully reflect the actual level of enterprises' innovation activity, especially in the context of the

shadow economy; the impact of external factors such as government policies supporting innovative entrepreneurship, the regulatory environment, and macroeconomic fluctuations requires further in-depth analysis, as they can have a decisive influence on the competitiveness of enterprises. Additionally, the role of digital transformation and business process automation should be considered, as these aspects were not sufficiently covered within this study. The prospect for further research is to investigate the impact of long-term planning of innovation activities on the level of competitiveness of business structures. Attention will be paid to assessing the effectiveness of strategic management of innovations in small and medium-sized

enterprises, a study that directly affects their competitive advantages and market share growth, their ability to adapt to crisis situations and maintain a stable market position.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the editor and reviewers for their assistance in preparing the article for publication.

FUNDING

The article by Shelenko D., *et al.* was prepared within the framework of the Iwan Wyhowski.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

REFERENCES

- [1] Agroportal. (2025a). *In the Lviv region, hummus is made from beans*. Retrieved from <https://agroportal.ua/news/eksklyuzivny-na-lvivshchini-z-kvasoli-robyat-humus>.
- [2] Agroportal. (2025b). *Three more biomethane plants will soon be operational in Ukraine*. Retrieved from <https://agroportal.ua/news/ukraina/v-ukrajini-nezabaram-zapracyuyut-shche-tri-biometanovi-zavodi>.
- [3] Agroportal. (n.d.a). *An onion cluster will be created in Ukraine*. Retrieved from <https://agroportal.ua/news/eksklyuzivny/v-ukrajini-stvoryat-cibuleviy-klaster>.
- [4] Agroportal. (n.d.b). *More than 60 water user organizations have already been created in Ukraine*. Retrieved from <https://agroportal.ua/news/ukraina/v-ukrajini-vzhe-svoreno-bilshe-60-oranzizaciy-vodokoristuvachiv>.
- [5] Al-Ababneh, H.A., Osmonova, A., Dumanska, I., Matkovskiy, P., & Kalynovskyy, A. (2021). Analysis of export of agricultural products in the context of the global food crisis. *Agricultural and Resource Economics: International Scientific E-Journal*, 7(4), 5-26. doi:10.51599/are.2021.07.04.01.
- [6] Babii, I.V., Baksalova, O.M. & Ostapchuk, O.V. (2022). The mechanism for the formation of the competitive policy of small enterprises in the post-war period. *Innovation and Sustainability*, 2, 123-130. doi:10.31649/ins.2022.2.123.130.
- [7] Balaniuk, I.F., & Ivaniuk, T.L. (2020). Land reforms in Ukraine: History of conduct. *Ekonomika APK*, 27(1), 111-120, doi:10.32317/2221-1055.202001111.
- [8] Brand Ukraine. (2022). *Annual report 2022*. Retrieved from https://brandukraine.org.ua/documents/50/ENG_Brand_Ukraine_Annual_report_2022.pdf.
- [9] Decyk, K. (2020). Competitiveness factors in the innovative enterprises in the North-East voivodeships in Poland. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 21(2), 503-518. doi:10.3846/btp.2020.12114.
- [10] Development Strategy of Ivano-Frankivsk Region for 2021-2027. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.if.gov.ua/storage/app/sites/24/documentu-2021/10-06-2021-strategiya-rozvitku-ivano-frankivskoi-oblasti-na-2021-2027-roki.pdf>.
- [11] George, K. (2024). *4 key takeaways from Google-parent Alphabet's earnings call*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/4-key-takeaways-from-google-parent-alphabet-earnings-call-8553147>.
- [12] Hotra, V. (2024). State instruments for stimulating entrepreneurship and supporting goods of essential social significance. *Actual Problems of Economics*, 10 (280), 135-144. doi:10.32752/1993-6788-2024-1-280-135-144.

- [13] Ivanova, M., Varyanichenko, O., Sannikova, S., & Faizova, S. (2018). Assessment of the competitiveness of enterprises. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 173(9-10), 26-31. [doi: 10.21003/ea.V173-01](https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V173-01).
- [14] Kapinos, H., & Larionova, K. (2025). Strategic management of innovative enterprise development as the basis for ensuring its competitiveness. *Herald of Khmelnytskyi National University. Economic Sciences*, 338(1), 564-573. [doi: 10.31891/2307-5740-2025-338-83](https://doi.org/10.31891/2307-5740-2025-338-83).
- [15] Korchynskiy, I.O., & Shchadylo, M.I. (2022). Research of the main methods for as-sessing the competitiveness of enterprises. *Social and Legal Studios*, 5(2), 54-60. [doi: 10.32518/2617-4162-2022-5-2-54-60](https://doi.org/10.32518/2617-4162-2022-5-2-54-60).
- [16] Kovalchuk, V. (2023). Analysis of trends in innovative development of the national economy. *Economy and Society*, 58. [doi: 10.32782/2524-0072/2023-58-33](https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2023-58-33).
- [17] Kozak, I., Mylenka, M., & Kozak-Balaniuk, I. (2024). Spatial analysis of cultural ecosystem services in Lublin: Perception of local residents and tourists. *Acta Scientiarum Polonorum Administratio Locorum*, 23(1), 101-113. [doi: 10.31648/aspal.9277](https://doi.org/10.31648/aspal.9277).
- [18] Kuzmin, T., Balaniuk, I., Shelenko, D., Shpykylak, O., & Smushak, M. (2024). [Economic assessment of agricultural enterprises in Ivano-Frankivsk region, Ukraine – identification of factors that influence performance](#). *Journal “Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development”*, 24(3), 497-508.
- [19] Milward, B. (2025). [International trade and sustainable development: Economic, historical, and moral arguments in favor of asymmetric global trade](#). Kyiv: Nash Format.
- [20] Monobank – chronicles of 2023. (2023). Retrieved from <https://projects.minfin.com.ua/monobank-pidsumky-2023-roku>.
- [21] Mukan, O.M., & Sharuk, A.M. (2021). Conceptual principles of evaluation of competitiveness of the enterprise in the conditions of entry into new international markets. *Management and Entrepreneurship in Ukraine*, 3(2), 91-98. [doi: 10.23939/smeu2021.02.091](https://doi.org/10.23939/smeu2021.02.091).
- [22] Nechyporenko, V.V. (2018). [Competition and competitiveness in the agricultural market of Ukraine](#). *Economics and Enterprise Management*, 3(14), 206-210.
- [23] OECD & Eurostat. (2018). *Oslo manual 2018*. Paris: OECD Publishing. [doi: 10.1787/9789264304604-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304604-en).
- [24] Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1163-p “On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Areas in Ukraine until 2030 and Approval of the Operational Action Plan for its Implementation in 2025-2027”. (2024, November). Retrieved from <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1163-2024-%D1%80#Text>.
- [25] PDCA cycle explained. Benefits, examples and expert advice. (2025). Retrieved from <https://ahaslides.com/uk/blog/pdca-cycle/>.
- [26] Personalized recommendations: How it helps to offer tailored streaming content. (2023). Retrieved from <https://www.alphansotech.com/blog/personalized-recommendations-how-it-helps-to-offer-tailored-streaming-content/>.
- [27] Pradhan, R.P., Arvin, M.B., Nair, M., & Bennett, S.E. (2020). The dynamics among entrepreneurship, innovation, and economic growth in the Eurozone countries. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 42(5), 1106-1122. [doi:10.1016/j.jpolmod.2020.01.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpolmod.2020.01.004).
- [28] Priss, O., Pugachov, M., Pugachov, V., Yaremko, I., & Shchabelska, V. (2023). The development of the world economy and the impact of the global food crisis 2022-2023, *Economic Affairs*, 68 (1s), 35-42. [doi:10.46852/0424-2513.1s.2023.5](https://doi.org/10.46852/0424-2513.1s.2023.5).
- [29] Pylypiv, N., & Sologub, S. (2024). Evaluation of the implementation of the strategy of social and economic development of territorial communities in the context of achieving sustainable development goals. *Journal of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University*, 11(4), 6-15. [doi: 10.15330/jpnu.11.4.6-15](https://doi.org/10.15330/jpnu.11.4.6-15).
- [30] Sas, L., Boryshkevych, I., Yakubiv, V., Maksymiv, Y., & Iwaszczuk, A. (2022). Methodical approach to complex evaluation of technological support of production in agricultural enterprises. *Proceedings on Engineering Sciences*, 4(4), 417-430. [doi:10.24874/PES04.04.004](https://doi.org/10.24874/PES04.04.004).

- [31] Shelenko, D., Shpykuliak, O., & Yemets, O. (2024). Conceptualization of the role of goods and services assessment in the management mechanism of agribusiness logistics structures. *International Scientific Journal "Internauka". Series: "Economic Sciences"*, 11. doi: 10.25313/2520-2294-2024-11-10502.
- [32] Slyvinska, O., & Bodnar, O. (2019). [Competitiveness agricultural products](#). *Economics and Management of the National Economy*, 3(14), 96-99.
- [33] Stakhiv, O.A., & Adamchuk, T.L. (2017). [Factors of competitiveness of an agricultural enterprise](#). *Economy and Society. Mukachevo State University*, 12, 360-365.
- [34] State Statistics Service of Ukraine. (n.d.b). *Innovative activities of enterprises*. Retrieved from <https://stat.gov.ua/uk/datasets/innovatsiyna-diyalnist-pidpryyemstv-1>.
- [35] The Ukrainian retail association has named the 15 largest e-commerce sellers. Spoiler: ROZETKA is leading by a significant margin. (2024). Retrieved from https://dev.ua/news/reitynh-naibilshykh-ryteileriv-1709823358#google_vignette.
- [36] Tulchynska, S., Vovk, O., Popelo, O., Saloid, S., & Kostyunik, O. (2021). Innovation and investment strategies to intensify the potential modernization and to increase the competitiveness of microeconomic systems. *IJCSNS International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, 21(6), 161-168. doi: 10.22937/IJCSNS.2021.21.6.22.
- [37] Ukraine – country performance, brand strength and reputation. (2024). Retrieved from <https://placebrandobserver.com/ukraine-country-performance-brand-strength-reputation/>.
- [38] Ukrainian truth. (2025). *An industrial park will appear in the Ternopil region, which will produce bioethanol and biogas*. Retrieved from <https://epravda.com.ua/biznes/na-ternopilshchini-buduyut-industrialniy-park-bio-lan-804846/>.
- [39] What does chewy do when your pet dies? (2023). Retrieved from <https://thefaithfuldog.com/what-does-chewy-do-when-your-pet-dies/>.
- [40] Yakymchuk, A., et al. (2021). Integral assessment of the level of Ukraine's economic security: Modeling and economic analysis. *Accounting*, 7(2), 381-390. doi: 10.5267/j.ac.2020.11.014.
- [41] YB Case. (2024). *Introduction to the topic of research and development*. Retrieved from <https://ybcase.com/ua/company-services/corporate-services/issledovania-i-razrobotki-rd-cto-nuzno-znat-v-2024-godu>.
- [42] Yehorov, I.Yu., et al. (2023). *Assessment of innovation development and structural transformations in the economy of Ukraine: Collective monograph*. Kyiv: National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, State Institution "Institute for Economics and Forecasting of the NAS of Ukraine".

Діана Шеленко

Доктор економічних наук, професор
Прикарпатський національний університет ім. Василя Стефаника
76000, вул. Шевченка, 57, м. Івано-Франківськ, Україна
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9214-7258>

Олександр Шпикуляк

Доктор економічних наук, професор
Національний науковий центр «Інститут аграрної економіки»
03127, вул. Героїв Оборони, 10, м. Київ, Україна
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5257-5517>

Іван Баланюк

Доктор економічних наук, професор
Прикарпатський національний університет ім. Василя Стефаника
76000, вул. Шевченка, 57, м. Івано-Франківськ, Україна
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8320-6383>

Геннадій Мазур

Доктор економічних наук, професор
Комунальний заклад вищої освіти «Вінницька академія безперервної освіти»
21050, вул. Грушевського, 13, м. Вінниця, Україна
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5061-1817>

Ярослав Бойчук

Аспірант
Прикарпатський національний університет ім. Василя Стефаника
76000, вул. Шевченка, 57, м. Івано-Франківськ, Україна
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-0793-905X>

Моніторинг і оцінка конкурентоспроможності продукції, товарів і послуг у контексті розвитку інноваційного підприємництва

Анотація. Інноваційне підприємництво є ключовим чинником економічної стабільності та конкурентоспроможності, що потребує вдосконалення інструментів прийняття рішень шляхом покращеного моніторингу та оцінки конкурентоспроможності продукції. Метою цього дослідження було теоретично та методологічно обґрунтувати й охарактеризувати інституційні можливості моніторингу конкурентоспроможності продукції, товарів і послуг у процесі розвитку структур інноваційного підприємництва. У межах дослідження були запропоновані концептуальні засади системи моніторингу конкурентоспроможності, аналітичні інструменти для оцінювання та прогнозування позицій підприємств, а також оціночна система, що враховує як внутрішні, так і зовнішні фактори впливу. Особливу увагу було приділено аналізу впливу цих чинників на ринкове позиціонування та функціональний розвиток інноваційних структур. У дослідженні вдосконалено методологічні основи моніторингу конкурентоспроможності, особливо в умовах інституційних трансформацій у середовищі ринкового обміну. Ключовим внеском стало впровадження комплексного підходу, який охоплює виробничі витрати, людські ресурси, інноваційний потенціал, фінансову стабільність, ринкову пропозицію та ефективність управління. Цей підхід вийшов за межі статичних вимірів і дав змогу врахувати структурну динаміку в часі, розкриваючи взаємозв'язки між різними чинниками конкурентоспроможності в різні

періоди та контексти. Поєднання кількісних і якісних інструментів оцінки забезпечило більш цілісний аналіз впливу внутрішніх і зовнішніх факторів на результати діяльності інноваційно орієнтованих підприємств і загальну ефективність підприємницької діяльності. Ключові виміри оцінки включали виробничу ефективність, людський капітал, інноваційні вкладення, фінансову стійкість, якість продукції та послуг, а також їхні синергічні ефекти. Отримані висновки є важливими для підвищення ефективності стратегічного та управлінського прийняття рішень в умовах стрімко змінюваного ринкового середовища. Практична значущість дослідження полягає у запропонуванні вдосконаленого механізму моніторингу та оцінювання конкурентоспроможності продукції, товарів і послуг у контексті розвитку інноваційного підприємництва

Ключові слова: економічне зростання; оцінка товарів і послуг; сталий розвиток; підприємець